

SORE THROAT IN ADULTS AND CHILDREN, SYMPTOMS, CAUSES, TREATMENT, TIPS

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Abstract. Sore throat Pain that increases with swallowing, as well as "scratching" of the throat, soreness and dryness in the throat - these are often complaints made by patients at the appointment of a therapist or otorhinolaryngologist. Such clinical signs are characteristic of many diseases. Before starting the treatment of pain in the throat, it is necessary to determine its cause, and this requires a detailed examination by a specialist. In most cases, pain in the throat is accompanied by other symptoms, including respiratory diseases (wheezing, cough), as well as fever and enlargement of local lymph nodes.

Keywords: causes and risk factors of sore throat, differential diagnosis, treatment of sore throat, what to do if you have a sore throat during pregnancy, what to do if you have a sore throat in children?

БОЛЬ В ГОРЛЕ У ВЗРОСЛЫХ И ДЕТЕЙ, СИМПТОМЫ, ПРИЧИНЫ, ЛЕЧЕНИЕ, СОВЕТЫ

Аннотация. Боль в горле. Боль, усиливающаяся при глотании, а также «першение» в горле, першение и сухость в горле – это частые жалобы больных на приеме у терапевта или оториноларинголога. Такие клинические признаки характерны для многих заболеваний. Перед началом лечения боли в горле необходимо определить ее причину, а для этого требуется детальное обследование у специалиста. В большинстве случаев боли в горле сопровождаются другими симптомами, в том числе респираторными заболеваниями (хрипы, кашель), а также лихорадкой и увеличением местных лимфатических узлов.

Ключевые слова: причины и факторы риска ангины, дифференциальная диагностика, лечение ангины, что делать при ангине при беременности, что делать при ангине у детей?

CAUSES AND RISK FACTORS OF SORE THROAT

A sore throat is often accompanied by diseases that develop against the background of weakened immunity. The causes of weakening of immunity can include excessive fatigue, lack of rational nutrition, hypovitaminosis, hormonal therapy, tumor chemotherapy, some chronic diseases (diabetes) and HIV.

If your sore throat is severe and painful when you swallow, you may be developing a cold or ARVI. These general pathologies are often accompanied by the development of an acute inflammatory process in the mucous membranes of the throat. There are the following general signs for ventilation:

An increase in body temperature up to 38.5 °C (usually 2-3 days after the appearance of discomfort in the nose and throat);

Tearing;

Nasal congestion and discharge from the nose (tomov);

Cough;

Moderate headache;
Muscle pain (not always).

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Specific symptoms for ARVI (also flu):

General weakness;

General weakness;

Bone stiffness;

Pain in the muscles;

An increase in body temperature above 38.5 ° C (from the first day of the disease). Often, sore throat is associated with the presence of a focus of chronic infections, especially in the sinuses (inflammatory diseases of the sinuses, sinusitis). Pathogenic microorganisms enter the throat from the source of infection and cause inflammation. A sore throat can be caused by seasonal or year-round allergic reactions. In such cases, the risk factor is the introduction of allergens into the respiratory tract (dust, house dust, etc.).

Smokers often suffer from sore throat. Ingestion of tobacco combustion products (including passive smoking) affects the mucous membrane.

A serious risk factor also includes occupational hazards. The disease can also develop as a result of constant inhalation of air contaminated with small mechanical particles and toxic chemical compounds. The throat can also be affected by infectious mononucleosis. Skin rashes, splenomegaly (enlargement of the spleen), neck and axillary lymph nodes are observed in this viral disease.

One of the possible causes of sore throat is atrophy of the mucous membrane of the larynx against the background of vitamin B12 deficiency anemia.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS

If the throat hurts and there is also ringing in the ear, the appearance of symptoms may be associated with the following diseases:

Otitis. In inflammation of the middle ear, fever, general weakness and loss of appetite are observed. The pain is worse in the evening.

Acute pharyngitis. In inflammation of the larynx, there is a feeling of the presence of a foreign body in the throat, "scratching" of the throat, and a dry cough. Pharyngitis often occurs together with ARVI.

Angina (Tonsillitis). This pathology is characterized by inflammation of the mucous membranes of the oropharynx and tonsils. In angina, there is a high fever, pain in the muscles, fever, and often an unpleasant smell from the mouth as a result of the purulent process.

Diphtheria. This disease is characterized by redness of the tonsils, the formation of a specific membrane in them, general intoxication of the body, and lymphadenitis. If a child

complains of a sore throat and enlarged lymph nodes, a doctor should be called immediately. Diphtheria is a life-threatening disease.

Other infectious diseases are children's diseases. These include scarlet fever, chicken pox and measles.

Important: If the throat hurts a lot and there is hoarseness, the reason may be that the inflammatory process due to pharyngitis, laryngitis and angina has affected the vocal apparatus. At the same time, hoarseness can occur as a result of straining the vocal cords (screaming or singing loudly); usually, in such a case, deterioration of general health is not observed.

If the throat hurts on one side, the reasons may be as follows:

Damage to the mucous membrane or the presence of a foreign body (for example, a fish bone);

Acute pharyngitis (at the initial stage of the disease, pain is noted only on the right or left side);

Retropharyngeal abscess (limited purulent inflammation);

Inflammation of the tonsils (acute tonsillitis);

Glossopharyngeal neuralgia;

Pathology of teeth and periodontal tissues associated with the focus of infection and inflammation;

Hilger's syndrome (enlargement of the peripheral branches of the external carotid artery).

One-sided sore throat in children may be due to the teething process. This sign in adults can be noted against the background of difficult eruption of "wisdom teeth" (that is, third molars).

If the throat hurts and there is no fever, it is possible that the following pathologies are present:

Damage to the mucous membrane (swallowing a hard or sharp object);

Tension of the vocal cords, as well as the muscles of the larynx and larynx;

Glossopharyngeal neuralgia;

Gastroesophageal reflux, that is, the release of stomach acid into the esophagus;

Development of tumors (oncology);

Thyroid pathology;

Itsenko-Cushing syndrome (hyperfunction of the adrenal glands);

Osteochondrosis of the cervical spine;

Varicose dilatation of esophageal veins.

A sore throat can be one of the symptoms of a developing myocardial infarction or angina attack!

TREATMENT OF SORE THROAT

A sore throat can often be treated at home. Before starting treatment, you should consult a doctor. First of all, visit a district therapist. Additional consultation of an otolaryngologist, dentist or other specialists may be required.

If inflammation of the throat has developed against the background of a cold or flu, it is recommended to gargle with chamomile, sage (sage) tinctures, soda, common salt or sea salt, hydrogen peroxide (1 teaspoon of 3% solution in 1 glass of water) . Garlic tincture (3 cloves of garlic in 200 ml of boiling water) also has a good therapeutic effect.

If the pain in the throat is very strong, it is impossible to swallow or there is shortness of breath, an ambulance should be called.

WHAT TO DO IF THROAT HURTS DURING PREGNANCY?

During pregnancy, serious changes occur in the body, which can cause a decrease in general immunity. Therefore, the mother has a high risk of streptococcal or staphylococcal infection, which often causes a sore throat.

Infectious agents can have a negative effect on the health of the fetus, so treatment should be started immediately. You should also consult a doctor when you experience any sore throat, because the causes of this sore throat can be much more serious than a common cold. In the course of treatment, it is possible to use drugs that are not only effective, but also safe for the fetus. The following therapeutic methods are recommended for sore throat during pregnancy:

Gargling with a solution of baking soda or table salt (1 tablespoon per 500 ml of water at room temperature);

Breathing (inhalation) with soda or chamomile tincture - 5-6 times a day until acute symptoms disappear;

Eating foods with more vitamin C to boost overall immunity.

Drink more fluids - it's even better if it's vitamin drinks or honey tea.

WHAT SHOULD BE DONE IF A CHILD HAS A SORE THROAT?

If the baby's throat hurts, you should consult a pediatrician. In the presence of this sign, it is very important to rule out dangerous viral diseases such as diphtheria and epidemic parotitis (chicken). If the child's throat lymph nodes are not enlarged and the redness of the throat is not strong, there is a possibility that the disease is of a viral nature (ORVI).

Sore throat in children

The main task in the treatment of viral infections is to stop the activity of the pathogen. Antiviral drugs are indicated. In order to prevent the disease and stop inflammation, inhalation with medicinal herbs and gargling are recommended. Antibiotics are completely ineffective in viral diseases; they can be prescribed only in cases of diagnosed secondary bacterial diseases. If the child is still small and cannot rinse himself, you can use an antiseptic aerosol.

Only a qualified doctor can prescribe drugs suitable for the child's age and condition. Bed rest is recommended for a sick child - at least in the first days after the onset of the disease. Transferring the disease to the "foot" is very dangerous for children, because the risk of developing complications is high.

Make sure that the sick child drinks as much liquid as possible - this will help to cleanse the child's body of toxins and prevent dehydration. It is not recommended to give sour juices to children, as they further irritate the already affected mucous membrane in the throat.

In case of inflammation of the throat, children often refuse to eat, because the pain becomes worse when swallowing. In this case, do not force the child to eat - it is better to give foods that do not affect the throat, for example, porridge, mashed soups, yogurt. It is recommended to eat food in small portions - less often.

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